

The Coupling Constant Series, Hadronic Density and 4D Manifolds

O Manor

June 9, 2021

Abstract:

The following is an analysis of the coupling constant primordial function. the analysis will focus on the variation cluster left to the Majestic (3), of the form: $(2N() + 3) + N_V$. The analysis will be done by using density sphere packing, to which we correlate the hadronic structure. The author regard this correlation as it was proven that the majestic (3) is the electron in the 8T framework. The new analysis than will allow new insight regarding the nature of the hadronic structure and overall better understanding of the 8T and the coupling constant series. We can also proof that the second term is an indication that there could not be more than four dimensions on our manifold.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.11)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (2.1)$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ...$$

Now, in the 8T framework, up to this point, we nicknamed the left term of each element in the coupling as a variation cluster, which is divisible by two and three to perfectly vanish into matter. This variation cluster is destabilized by the majestic three, causing a net variation to appear, or in other words, to boson propagation from the fermion. Recently one noticed a very interesting fact, that the left terms of the coupling constant series for the weak interaction are identical to densest packing D_4 highest kissing number that is 24. So all the left coupling terms are actually 4D spheres, leading to a propagation of the electron. That may sound outrageous but not in the 8T, as we only have 4D manifold, three spatial and one temporal.

By looking at the coupling constant in that light, we can also regard the hadron as possessing an extreme density, as it has the highest kissing number in 4D, and the electron is not bound to it but revolves around it, as the majestic is a separate term. The following apply to each other term:

$$24 * 5 \rightarrow 120 \quad (3)$$

$$24 * 5 * 7 \rightarrow 840 \quad (4)$$

Notice that those numbers are associated with highest kissing numbers in higher dimensions.

$$E_8 \rightarrow 240 = 120 * 2 \quad (5)$$

$$p_{12} \rightarrow 840 \quad (6)$$

Of course, ignoring the higher dimensions complexity and focusing on the part of the highest kissing numbers, we can reach an insight, those fermionic clusters in each term are most dense, in agreement with what we know about the structure of the fermions, and in particular the hadron. Also, notice that those higher dimensions are scalar four multiples, which as one believes, means that should appear on the manifold eventually. The highest kissing number in D_4 is the base to all other kissing numbers at those higher dimensions. By looking at the coupling constant series, than we can correlate the manifold and validate it has only four dimensions, since all higher terms are the dimension four multiples of the kissing number, 24. And thus there could not be more than four dimensions on our manifold. There are of course other manifolds, which according to the series are four dimensional as well, interacting with our own as given by the main equation of the 8T. But by coupling constant series, it is possible to derive why the manifold has exactly four dimensions, because of the kissing number of the second term and above.

$$D_4^{24} * 5 = (E_8^{240} / 2) \quad (7)$$

$$D_4^{24} * 35 = 840 \quad (8)$$

References

[1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

[2] J.H.CONWAY, N.J.A SLOANE. "SHPERE PACKINGS, LATTICES AND GROUPS" In: (1999)